

Review of *Postcolonialism Now: Literature, Reading, Decolonising* by Sourit Bhattacharya. Hyderabad: Orient Blackswan, 2025. Paperback. 272 pages. ISBN 9789354426568. Rs. 620.

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In today's world, it becomes exigent to re-interrogate the role of the postcolonial critic's handling of terms such as 'anticolonial', 'decolonial' and 'postcolonial', and whether these theoretical terms are efficient in comprehending the contemporary world-historical processes. That postcolonialism, as a theoretical rubric, was instantiated to question the historical elision of the imperialist powers and celebrate the hybridity of the colonised subject has already imbibed critical interventions at several levels, with the term accumulating several strands of signification and moving beyond its intended ambit to engage with the complexities of representation and lived experiences in a post-national, post-capitalist, post-liberal, global space. Therefore, it accrues immense significance to understand the contemporary theatres of critical engagement and the dialectics of empowerment that the theoretical rubric of postcolonialism seeks to achieve. Sourit Bhattacharya's newly published book, *Postcolonialism Now: Literature, Reading, Decolonising* attempts to trace the trajectory of postcolonialism in the contemporary world through his contrapuntal reading of global Anglophone Literatures.

Dr. Bhattacharya's recent intellectual pursuit is not another rendition to the already established canon of postcolonial scholarship, but an intervention which relies on the novel methodology of 'reading' as a counter strategy to tackle the problematics of representation in the genre of postcolonial literature. The book derives its significance from

the fact that it does not approach literary studies from the vantage point of critical theoretical intervention, but inverts the scholarly inclination and posits the literary text as a path to theoretical complexity. Such an approach effectively decenters postcolonialism from the encumbrances of theoretical strictures and amplifies it at the crossroads of creative impulses and cultural connotations, thereby reinforcing the idea that the concept of postcolonialism is at the stage where re-intervention and re-imagination become critical tool to assess the efficacy of the theoretical model. The title of the book pre-emptively foreshadows its broader ambition of developing vis-à-vis augmenting a praxis of decolonisation by probing the interstices postcolonialism and decolonial practices. Essentially, the book attempts to enhance the agenda of decolonisation through a contrapuntal reading of global Anglophone Literature through the five distinct rubrics of minorities, migrations, traumas, ecologies and futures in the postcolonial context, and thereby builds a ballast of ideologies that provokes a multidimensional solidarity across the frontiers of nation, caste, race, sexuality and ecology. In the ensuing portion of the article, I will further discuss how Bhattacharya's book harnesses the tripartite methodology of literature, reading and decolonising to fathom the contours of postcolonialism now.

To resist the colonial matrix of power, which destitutes the praxis of the lived experiences of the colonised subject and proposes a rampant marching of western modernity at the expense of a muted colonised subject's historiography (Mignolo 2020), it is incumbent to establish modes of dialogue, a reparative modernity, between the critical concepts of the decolonial and postcolonial. However, it would be prudent to exhort that such dialogues already exist which takes into consideration the negotiations between decoloniality and postcolonialism. Postcolonialism, as an intellectual movement, addressed the issues of the material and socio-economic realities, seeking to retrieve the colonised subject from the complex "Orient" and instantiating redressal mechanism that co-opts the colonised subject's historiography. Decoloniality, on the other hand, has gleaned from the theoretical

moulds of world-systems theory, development and underdevelopment theory and the Frankfurt School of Critical Social Theory, stressing the needs to challenge the insularity of historical narratives and historiographical traditions emanating from Europe. Though divergent in terms of scholarly predilections, disciplinary affiliations and geographic boundaries, the discernible critical units of decoloniality and postcolonialism concedes convergences in the radical potentialities of unsettling and reconstituting the hegemonic process of epistemology and pedagogy. In a conjoined effort to interrogate the aesthetics of “value-coding” (Spivak 2000) and seeking to understand the geopolitics of knowledge, the dialectics between decoloniality and postcolonialism enunciates the practices of knowledge that has been relegated due to hegemonic exhortations of western modernity. It is imperative here to concur with Walter D. Mignolo that epistemology is not ahistorical but epistemology has to be “geographical in its historicity.” (Mignolo 2005) Therefore, decolonial epistemic shifts intervenes into the indigenous cultural matrix prior to European incursions to retrieve the colonised subject’s historiography. Bhattacharya’s latest book takes the gauntlet to the imperial centres which propagated hegemonic western modernity and seeks to unfurl the dismantling of hierarchical colonial practices from within the ambit of western academia and creative-cultural industry, though colonialism, in the contemporary world, has changed its shape to neoimperialism and engages in neocolonial practices with the sovereign nation-states across the world. In his insistence, and, more importantly, his subjectivity, Bhattacharya traces, if not celebrates, literature’s potential for a cultural emancipation with decolonial thinkers acting at the very centre of imperialism. Thus, in the new geopolitics of knowledge that Bhattacharya seeks to instantiate, hierarchical and hegemonic practices are divested and dismantled in the very geographies which preached and advanced the homogenising enterprise of western modernity. Taking the rubrics of nation, caste, race, sexuality and ecology, Bhattacharya problematises the issues of representation of postcolonial Anglophone literature. In effect, Bhattacharya’s methodology of decoloniality is a complimentary image of indigenous

studies, wherein the very nature of decoloniality “delinks” the endogenous conceptuality of colonialism.

Bhattacharya’s project of the retrieval of the colonised subjects begins at foregrounding “reading” as a discursive site of knowledge production. The act of reading a diversified set of literary persona and cultural commentators brings to the fore the acknowledgement of alterity, which is very crucial for the formation of a non-dualist collectivity; a sociocultural solidarity that upends the binary of the educator and the educated, thereby facilitating participation into local and indigenous forms of thinking, and the subsequent examination of one’s positionality. The rhetoric of the coloniser can be only be resisted through a reappraisal of colonial histories and knowledge systems, and Bhattacharya posits “reading” as a material practice and epistemological site to achieve the desired revision of the colonialist knowledge systems. Therefore, the critical act of “reading” complicates the homogenising tendencies of colonial enterprise and reaffirms the positionality of literary texts to interrogate the structures of transformation, thereby extending their reach and influence into the realms of critical theory. In a similar vein of transdisciplinary permeability, Bhattacharya opines, “... my reading is not solely aimed at reception or the effect that literary works have created among readers. It interrogates history through style; politics through aesthetics; context through form; and, above all, the postcolonial through the anticolonial for which a historical materialist method is warranted.” (Bhattacharya 2025)

In an academic world, which is almost afflicted with a “explosion of theory,” Bhattacharya’s project reserves its right to recognition because it achieves decoloniality through an amalgamation of materialist act of reading with the historicising process of the anticolonial movement. In his own admission, Bhattacharya methodology posits a similarity with Benita Parry’s reading of British colonial literature, but Bhattacharya’s project marks its novelty in its adjudication of the essence of location in the act of reading. Therefore, as already mentioned, Bhattacharya concentrates on those literary expressions which are borne as a result of

colonial or neocolonial practices, and are effected by those agents whose geographic residence are the urban and/or imperial centres. Therefore, the method of conception, circulation, reception and perception happen in diffused geographic locale but the production of these expressions is at the imperial centres; aligned with a historical materialist form of reading. Such an arrangement of the critical-creative practices evokes a multidimensionality of neocolonial oppression and, simultaneously empowers one to resist the dehumanising experiences of social marginalisation. The significance of this project lies in its contemporaneity, both in its selection of the literary texts for discussion and the engagement with these texts along the prevailing lines of world-historical processes, and in its underlying ambitions of creating methodologies which overrides the strategies of segmentation, thereby establishing a social relation of totality.

Works Cited

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